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ALTERNATIVE LEARNING SYSTEM PROFESSIONALS: A SUCCESS STORY

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ABSTRACT

This study narrates the challenges encountered and the motivating factors of Alternative Learning Systems who are already professionals in the West Tacurong Cluster, Schools Division of Tacurong City this school year 2022-2023. It employed a phenomenological study using thematic analysis in processing the responses of the participants.

On the Challenges encountered by the Alternative Learning System professionals, the themes were generated, Financial Problem, Working Student, Parents' Occupation, and visual disability and Bullying.

On the motivating factors that ALS Learners experienced following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants Getting a degree before getting married, Dream and pray, Scholarship Program, and Family Support.

Keywords: *Alternative Learning System, Professionals, Success Story, Tacurong City, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), literacy is a fundamental human right and the foundation for lifelong learning. It is a prerequisite for ensuring an evolving global society and contributes to national and human development. Countries that are successful in giving their population literacy and lifelong skills are usually in a better position to meet the economic demands of operating in a globalized information economy (Apao, Dayagbil & Abao, 2014). With this context,

individuals must be literate to become globally competitive but to accomplish this lies in the education process.

The Philippine government subsequently implemented the Alternative Learning System (ALS) under the jurisdiction of the Department of Education as a necessary component of the Philippine education system to provide each and every Filipino with unrestricted access to basic education to decrease the illiteracy rate as proposed in the Education for All (EFA) 2015 Philippine Plan of Action. The Alternative Learning System is conceptualized as a non-formal modular education program that caters to the learning needs of non-schoolers, dropouts, illiterate adults, and other learners from marginalized groups who have never experienced formal education but can learn in an out-of-school setting.

In the School Division Office of Tacurong City, there are the products of the Alternative Learning System who are now professionals in their fields, but there is no conducted study on the success of the program and the life of those professionals in Tacurong City.

Thus, the primary focus of this study is to assess and understand the complex issues and success stories in the Alternative Learning System of the Schools Division Office of Tacurong City that can provide a detailed description of the specific and rare cases of the Alternative Learning System teachers and completers.

Research Questions

This study aims to find out the issues, concerns, and success stories of the Alternative Learning System teachers and completers in the Schools Division Office of Tacurong City.

Specifically, it will seek the following questions;

1. Describe the challenges encountered by the Alternative Learning System professionals.
2. Narrate the motivating factors that ALS Learners experienced.

METHODOLOGY

This investigation employed a phenomenological research design as it can study people's experiences, how people construct meaning in their lives, and commonalities that transverse individuals experiencing a specific phenomenon (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017). Notably, this study utilized Transcendental phenomenology, which aimed to seek understanding in human experience, which is performed by laying aside prepossessed ideas in order to view the phenomena to be investigated through a new lens, allowing it to immerge, giving its distinct meaning and form.

The focus participants of this study are eight (8) completers of the Alternative Learning System whose already professionals in their field, they are four-year graduates of college and work in different industries, who were selected through purposive sampling. This phenomenological study selected seven (7) participants that fit the suggestion of

Creswell (2014) as an ample number of participants to generate meaningful themes and valuable interpretations.

RESULTS

On the challenges encountered by the Alternative Learning System professionals

The Alternative Learning System Learners now are already professionals in their chosen endeavor and share the challenges they encountered in completing the program and their challenges in getting their college diploma.

The following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, **a. Financial Problem, b. Working Student, c. Parents' Occupation, and d. visual disability and Bullying.**

Narrate the motivating factors that ALS Learners experienced

In terms of the motivating factors that ALS learners experienced and their road to becoming a professional is worth remembering. The following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants **a. Getting a degree before getting married, b. Dream and pray, c. Scholarship Program, and Family Support.**

DISCUSSION

On the Challenges encountered by the Alternative Learning System professionals

The following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants, **a. Financial Problem, b. Working Student, c. Parents' Occupation, and d. visual disability and Bullying.**

The first theme that was generated was the **financial problem**

As the participants share the challenges they encountered:

"Hello! Good Evening, 2014 ALS graduate, and I took Bachelor of Secondary Education, Major in English at SMIT. Well based on my experience during my college days was never easy kasi there were some hindrances na muntik na akong maka-stop but despite that I am very grateful kasi meron akong mama na nagpu push through sa akin throughout the entire college life never sumuko. Well, typically hindi naman natin ma..., kung бага walang exemption sa lahat-lahat ng struggles nayan like you'll face maraming challenges like financial problems, yong mga ganap sa buhay magbi breakthrough ka, you're going to have some

depression and in my case kasi, well sa akin kasi sir before ako nag-take ng ALS is nagka-anak ako at very young age and then my mom said na if gusto ko mag pursue to college I'll take ALS so". **Participants 1, Female**

A second theme generated was, **working students**, most of the participants were working students that why they experience challenges while completing the program.

"Maraming pag-subok na akong nadaanan sa buhay upang maipasa ito pero hindi ako nag-alinlangan upang makamit ko ito. Unang una sa lahat gumawa ako ng set as a goal upang hindi ako mapariwara kahit na subsob ako sa trabaho pero kailangan ko parin, as may goal ka kailangan mong gawin yon as a guide. And then, hindi rin ako nagpatinag sa mga problema na dumaan sa buhay ko kasi maraming mga nagmomotivate sa akin na makapagtapos kagaya ng aking mga pamilya, si Ma'am Rodella siya yong nagpursue na kailangang talagang magtapos upang hindi basta basta na, upang hindi masayang yong kanilang mga pinaghirapan sa amin". **Participants 3, Male**

The third theme that was generated was **Parents' Occupations**. Participants share the challenges they experience with their parents' occupation.

"Sa hirap ng buhay pahinto- hinto ang aking pag –aaral, hindi kayang tustusan ng aking mga magulang ang aking pag-aaral dahil pa ekstra-ekstra lang sa trabaho ang aking ama. Malapit na sana akong magkapagtapos ng hayskul ngunit sinubok ako ng katatagan sa larangan ng pag-ibig. Hindi naging madali ang buhay may asawa. Nakaranas kami ng matinding kahirapan. Nabuhay kami sa pagiging kargador ng aking asawa sa palengke. Doon ko napagtanto na kung nakatapos lamang ako sa pag-aaral hindi namin mararansasan ang ganoong sitwasyon. Muling nabuhay ang aking pangarap na makapagtapos ng pag-aaral at makapagsuot ng itim na toga". **Participant 5, Female**

The fourth theme that was generated **visual disability and bullying**

"My father is a farmer and my mother is a plain housewife. I was born with a visual disability due to a congenital cataract. This caused me to experience many difficulties in doing daily life activities such as recognizing and familiarizing different faces or objects which is essential to establish permanent social relationships. I inherited this disability from my mother and also to four of my siblings.

During my childhood, I was always experienced being bullied by other children due to my condition. I was also look down and prejudged by other people that I have no good future and will always be dependent until I get older. It did not stop me from dreaming of going to school.

Despite of my situation, I never lose hope. I always dream and pray to God that someday I will become a productive person and will be in school again. Someday, people will change their way of perception, especially to those like me". **Participant 6, Male, Soldier**

Narrate the motivating factors that ALS Learners experienced

Alternative schools with merit for impacting student success and program completion are designed to meet the needs of a specific at-risk population; consequently the adults that work with these students must exhibit specific attributes in order to address their needs. Every teacher employed in an alternative setting must choose to be there and possess a passion to support the at-risk youth in their personal and educational endeavor (Mottaz, 2002).

In terms of the motivating factors that ALS learners experienced and their road to becoming a professionals is worth remembering. The following themes were generated based on the responses of the participants **a. Getting a degree before getting married, b. Dream and pray, c. Scholarship Program, and Family Support.**

The first motivating factor that was generated was **Getting a degree before getting married**, participants believe that they can get a decent job if they have a diploma after which they can settle their own family. The participants were happy to narrate their motivating factors while interviewing the participants. As they share:

“Sabi ko sa sarili ko kailangan ko makagraduate kasi yong mga anak ko kailangan ako. And then that time it’s not easy kasi hindi ko alam kung kanino ko iiwan yong mga bata, nag-aabsent pa ko sir kasi walang magbantay hindi ko alam kung saan sila iwan, tapos kulang pa yong pera, yong pamasaha kaya hindi siya madali na inuna ko yong to have kids, to have my own family bago yong...pinagsabay ko yong studies ko. It’s very very hard kaya nga always kong inaadvised sa mga nakababata sa akin, sa mga students kailangan nilang makagraduate muna bago magbuild ng kanilang family kasi makakahintay rin yan”. **Participant 1, Female**

Dream and pray is the second theme that was generated based on the responses of the participants. As the participants narrate their experiences.

“Despite of my situation, I never lose hope. I always dream and pray to God that someday I will become a productive person and will be in school again. Someday, people will change their way of perception, especially to those like me. Luckily in 2005, I underwent eye surgery sponsored by somebody who has a big heart for people like me. I could now see a little bit through my right eye. The doctor said that they could longer totally regain his eyesight due to a hereditary condition. It already gave me a little hope that I could already go to school again. I learned how to write my name with my brother’s assistance. After that, I persistently requested my mother to send me to school. All I want was to be able to read, write and count, after that, I would already stop”. **Participant 6, Male**

Some participants are motivated by their family and friends while others pursue education because of **the Scholarship Program** which is the third theme that was generated in the responses of the participants. As they share;

“Tong nabal.an namon nga nakapasa ako sa ALS nagdirect kami ni Mamang sa Quezon Colleges of Southern Philippines didto ko nagpaenrol sa course ko nga BEED tapos from first year to fourth year. Pag first year college ko ang tanan nga baydanan namon sila mamang kag papang ang gabayad from 1st sem to 2nd sem, pero pag-abot ko sa Second Year College nag-apply ko sa scholarship program kay Gov. Pax Mangudadatu and then yon natanggap ako that’s why pagkasecond year college hanggang sa fourth year college ko naging scholar po ako ni Pax Mangudadatu tapos marami ding stuggles yong mga naranasan ko bago po ako nakagraduate sa ALS. Paggraduate ko ng college actually during pandemic didto nagstruggles din kami during pandemic kay budlayan man si papang kapangita sang obra niya kay nagstop pa kay pandemic pa siya so, didto kami nabudlayan sa pandemic tapos pag-abot sa ano naggraduate ako sa college wala kami nakamarcha kay naabutan kami pandemic sato. And then, after that pagka 2022 nagreview ako sa CVRC kay ano magtake ako ng board exam for teachers then after that pagka October 2022 pasado po sa Licensure Examination for teachers po”. **Participants 4, Female**

Family Support is the most important thing in everything you do because the members of the family are the happiest person if you reach your goal in life family support is the last theme that was generated. As the participants narrate their experiences;

“And then, hindi rin ako nagpatinag sa mga problema na dumaaan sa buhay ko kasi maraming mga nagmomotivate sa akin na makapagtapos kagaya ng aking mga pamilya, si Ma’am Rodella siya yong nagpursue na kailangang talagang magtapos upang hindi basta basta na, upang hindi masayang yong kanilang mga pinaghirapan sa amin. Kailangan naming talaga makapagtapos sa pag-aaral hindi nila yon ginawa para sa kanila kundi ginawa nila yon para sa amin upang maipagmalaki din niya kami na ganito ALS passer namin ito graduate college na. so, ah yong parents ko din tumutulong din siya sa pag-aaral namin kahit na alam namin na kapos din siya kasi marami kaming magkakapatid so ang ginawa ko that time is nagworking student ako sa James kahit na mahirap pero kailangang kayanin upang maipasa ito at yon lang po at maraming Salamat”. **Participant 3, Male**

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

The following themes were generated a. Financial Problems, b. Working Student, c. Parents' Occupation, and d. visual disability and Bullying on the challenges encountered by ALS professionals

The motivating factors are getting a degree before getting married, the Dream and pray, Scholarship Program, and Family Support.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented:

The Alternative Learning Program may continue its best practices in catching the out-of-school youth to address the no one would left behind. The teachers may sustain their best practices in handling and motivating Alternative Learning System students to sustain the program for out-of-school youth. The Alternative Learning System Professionals may give priority to the job hiring placement in any organization. This study be replicated in wide scope to have a clearer picture of the implementation of Alternative Learning Systems quantitatively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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